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Motivation And Organizational Productivity: A Study Of Nnamdi Azikiwe University Libraries, 2018-2023

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the motivation and organizational productivity: A study of Nnamdi Azikwe University Libraries. The study is anchored on goal setting theory. The study adopted survey method of research. Data were generated through primary and secondary sources. The method for data collection was questionnaire which was administered randomly among the staff of the selected libraries. The populations of the study were 163; the sample size of the study is one hundred and sixty-three (163). While one hundred and fifty-three (153) were retrieved. The hypotheses were tested using t-test at 0.05% level of significance. The findings of the study revealed, financial incentive has significant effect on organizational productivity of Nnamdi Azikwe University Libraries; Promotion has significant effect on organizational productivity of Nnamdi Azikwe University Libraries; Work environment has significant effect on organizational productivity of Nnamdi Azikwe University Libraries. The study recommends that Employees should be trained according to the present content of the environment. Management should provide effective incentive plan to their employees from time to time to boost their morale for enhanced productivity and performance. Management should publicly recognize the efforts of their employees to induce their performance in the work place.

Keywords: Financial incentives, promotion, work environment, motivation and productivity

INTRODUCTION

Every organization employs some form of motivational strategy to get their employees to do their best to achieve their mission and vision. Some organizations assume that the motivational strategy they use is appropriate for all employees and leads to the achievement of goals. In today's competitive business environment, every organization regardless of size or market, strives to gain a competitive advantage and achieve good results. To achieve this, it is important for the organization to clearly define its goals and know how to do so making use of available resources. The most integral aspect of an organization is the human resources. Employees are the ones who make use of their skills and knowledge to provide support to the organization as a way of achieving goals. Organizations that consider their employees as the core of the business and continuously improve employee motivation and performance tends to be more effective (Lawani et al, 2024).

Motivation is the key to creating an enabling environment where optimal performance is possible. with the present global economic trend, most employers of labour have realized the fact that for their organizations to compete favourably, the performance of their employees goes a long way in determining the success of the organization. On the other hand, performance of employees in any organization is vital, not only for the growth of the organization, but also for the growth of individual employees (Eze, 2019). An organization must know who their outstanding workers, those who need

additional training and those not contributing to the efficiency and welfare of the company or organization (Ali, Abrar & Haider, 2012).

Motivation and productivity are two concepts that continue to attract interest from scholars, practitioners, and business owners. Motivation has been argued to play a key role in an employee's work productivity in organisations as they strive to achieve their goals. With the world rapidly changing organisations today are also continually striving to find efficient ways of working that will ensure that their employees are more productive but more importantly that the employees are motivated (Mwaba & Abubaker, 2024). Motivation will, most of the times enable the worker or employee of an organization to seriously do his duties and responsibilities (Azar and Shafiqhi, 2013). Attractive Salary or pay is also a Valuable tool that plays an important role to increase employee's performance and also increase the productivity of an organization (Muogbo, U.S, 2013).

Statement of the Problem

In a highly competitive, global environment, organizations are constantly under pressure to retain their workforce (Deci, 2013). Highly skilled, reliable and experienced employees are a valuable asset for any organization. It is evident that highly motivated employees are more likely to have high productivity. However, according to Certo (2006), good performance is not as a result of motivation only, but also includes ability i.e. skills, equipment, supplies and time. Some organizations have been known to experience a high staff turnover despite offering above average salaries (Aguinis, 2012). This tells us that money is not the only way to motivate employees. Additionally, different people are motivated by different factors. It is important for managers and supervisors to understand what motivates individual employees, and not assume a one-size-fits-all approach (George and Jones, 2013). An organization is only as strong as its workforce.

Motivation is the driving force that helps individuals achieve their goals. However, many people struggle with staying motivated and this can lead to missed opportunities and unfulfilled potential. There are several common motivational challenges that individuals face and they include; lack of direction or clarity in goals. When individuals find themselves lacking direction or clarity in their goals, it can be difficult to stay motivated and make progress. Again is the problem of procrastination and feeling overwhelmed and it can lead to a lack of motivation and hinder progress towards achieving goals. The fear of failure or rejection can be a significant obstacle that can prevent individuals from pursuing their goals and achieving success. It can also lead to feelings of self-doubt, demotivation, and even anxiety. Lastly, lack of support or accountability can be a significant obstacle that can make it challenging for individuals to stay motivated and achieve their goals.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the effect of motivation on organizational productivity: A study of Nnamdi Azikwe University Libraries. The specific objectives of the study are to:

- i. Determine the effect of financial incentives on organizational productivity of Nnamdi Azikwe University Libraries.
- ii. Investigate the degree to which promotion affects organizational productivity of Nnamdi Azikwe University Libraries.
- iii. Evaluate the effect of work environment on organizational productivity of Nnamdi Azikwe University Libraries.

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses will be formulated to guide the objectives of the study and strengthen the analysis

- i. Ho₁: Financial incentive has no significant effect on organizational productivity of Nnamdi Azikwe University Libraries.
- ii. Ho₂: Promotion has no significant effect on organizational productivity of Nnamdi Azikwe University Libraries.
- iii. Ho₃: Work environment has no significant effect on organizational productivity of Nnamdi Azikwe University Libraries.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Theoretical Framework

This work is anchored on goal setting theory by Locke and Latham 2002.

Goal-Setting

A goal is the aim of an action or task that a person consciously desires to achieve or obtain (Locke and Latham, 2002). Goal setting is a motivational technique used extensively in organizations as a method of directing individuals' efforts at work and providing a standard against which performance can be assessed (Lunenberg, 2011). Since it was first researched five decades ago, goal-setting theory has been the most researched, utilized, and established theory of work motivation in the field of industrial and organizational psychology (Buchanan, 2012). Goal-setting theory was developed inductively within industrial/organizational (I/O) psychology over a 25-year period, based on some 400 laboratory and field studies (Locke and Latham, 2002; 2006). Goal setting is a cognitive theory of motivation based on the premise that people have needs that can be thought of as specific outcomes or goals they hope to obtain (Locke and Latham, 1990). The theory started with the initial work on levels of aspiration developed by Kurt Lewin and has since been primarily developed by Dr. Edwin Locke, who began goal setting research in the 1960s (Redmond, 2015). Kurt Lewins' early work on "level of aspiration" provided the foundation for the most researched and well-established theory of work motivation- goal-setting theory (Levy, 2013).

Goal- setting theory emphasizes the role of specific, challenging performance goals and workers' commitment to those goals as key determinants of motivation (Newstrom, 2011). Goal setting theory has guided the development of an immense body of empirical research about workplace motivation, and it is by far the dominant paradigm in the literature today (Kurose, 2013). According to Lunenberg (2011), goal setting is the underlying explanation for all major theories of work motivation- whether that is Vroom's VIE theory, Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs theory, Herzberg's motivation theory or Bandura's social cognitive theory. Goal setting has also been identified as one of the most effective methods of changing behavior in the workplace (Skinner, 2010). Goal setting theory is a framework for understanding the relationships among motivation, behavior, and performance (Kurose, 2013). Managers generally accept goal setting as a means to enhance and sustain performance (Dubrin, 2012). Locke and Latham's goal setting theory states that several conditions are particularly important in successful goal achievement. These include goal acceptance and commitment, goal specificity, goal difficulty, and feedback (Redmond, 2015). Goal-setting theory states that for employees to be motivated, goals must be clear, specific, attainable and whenever possible, quantified (Riggio, 2014).

Application

A goal is defined simply as what the individual is consciously trying to do (Lunenberg, 2011). Newstrom (2013) outlines goals as targets and objectives for future performance that help focus employees attention on items of greater importance to the organization, encourage better planning for the allocation of critical resources (e.g. time money and energy), illustrate the value of persistent effort, and stimulate the preparation of action plans for goal attainment. Research on goal-setting has also stressed the importance of getting workers committed to goals, for without such commitment, it is unlikely that goal setting will be motivating (Riggio, 2014). Evidence suggests that if workers participate in goal setting, as opposed to having supervisors set the goals, there is increased motivation (Gomez-Mejia, Balkin, and Cardy, 2015).

Empirical Review

Nwangwu, & Nwangwu, (2023) looked at how women working in Anambra states deposit money banks' organizational sustainability in relation to work-life balance. The study looked at how the work atmosphere, employee assistance, flexible scheduling, and leave policies affected the performance of female employees. Review of pertinent theoretical and empirical literatures. The study's foundation was Border Theory. Data were gathered for the study from both primary and secondary sources. The study's sample included 953 women from selected deposit money institutions.92% of the 873 copies of the questionnaires that were properly completed and submitted were returned. Utilizing NOVA, hypotheses were evaluated. According to the data, the leave policy has a considerable positive impact on the organizational sustainability of female employees at deposit money institutions in the state of

Anambra. Flexible scheduling significantly improves the organizational sustainability of female employees in Anambra state's deposit money banks.

Nwangwu, (2024) examined point of sales (POS) business and unemployment reduction in Awka, Anambra state.. The sources of data for this research were mainly primary data and secondary data. The population of this study comprised of registered Point of Sales (POS) business in Awka south L.G.A. Thus, the total population of the study comprises of two thousand five hundred and forty (2,540) registered operators in Awka south.

While 400 sample size was gotten using taro Yamane formular. Statistics such as frequency count and percentages were put to use in the analysis of research questions while research hypotheses were tested using correlation analysis and simple regression analysis. The findings of the study revealed thus; Table base POS business positively influences unemployment reduction in Awka, Anambra state; Mobile POS business reduces unemployment rate in Awka, Anambra state; Online POS business has no significant effect on unemployment reduction in Awka, Anambra state.

Muyiwa, Okeke & Nwangwu, (2023). examined the job redesign and employee productivity in Vegetable oil firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. The study adopted survey method of research. Data were generated through primary and secondary sources. The method for data collection was questionnaire which was administered randomly among the staff of the selected vegetable oil firm. The population of the study was 942; the sample size of the study was the same population because it is not up to 1000. While eight hundred and seventy-three (873) were retrieved. The hypotheses were tested using regression analysis method at 0.05% level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that, Job enrichment has a significant and positive effect on employee commitment of vegetable oil firms; Job enlargement has a significant and positive effect on employee commitment of vegetable oil firms.

Nwangwu, J.C (2023) examined the role of entrepreneurship in enhancing employment in a developing society, a study of Oyi L.G.A in Anambra State. The research is anchored on Joseph Schumpeter's Theory of Entrepreneurship. The study adopted survey method of research. Data were generated through primary and secondary sources. The method for data collection was questionnaire which was administered randomly among the youth of Oyi LG. The population of the study was 168,029, while sample sizes of 399 were determined using Taro Yamane. The hypotheses were tested using ANOVA at 0.05% level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that: Access to finance has significant effect in enhancing employment in Oyi L.G.A in Anambra State; Skill acquisition has significant effect in enhancing employment in Oyi L.G.A in Anambra State; Government policies have significant effect in enhancing employment in Oyi L.G.A in Anambra State.

Nwangwu, (2022) examined Assessment of Factors Affecting Performance of Women Entrepreneurship in Aguata LGA. The study is anchored on Socio-cultural Theory. The study adopted survey method of research. Data were generated through primary and secondary sources. The method for data collection was questionnaire which was administered randomly among the women of Aguata LGA. The population of the study was 35,202, while sample sizes of 677 were determined using Borg & Gall formular. The hypotheses were tested using ANOVA at 0.05% level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that Socio-cultural factor has no significant effect on the performance of women entrepreneurship in Aguata LGA., F-test of 1.742 and probability value of .915 Economic factors has significant effect on the performance of women entrepreneurship in Aguata LGA, F-test of 9.233 and probability value of 0.000. Financial factors has significant effect on the performance of women entrepreneurship in Aguata LGA., T-test of 7.807 and probability value of 0.008.

Nwangwu, Ohanyere; Nwangwu & Atueyi, (2025) examined the effect of artificial intelligent (AI) on decision-making in supply chain management of lubricant firms in Anambra state, Nigeria. The study was anchored on Technology Acceptance Theory (TAT). A structure questionnaire was developed for data collection. The population of the study comprised of 281 management staff from thirteen (13) lubricant firms in Anambra State. Two hundred and sixty-nine (269) were duly filled and returned data was analysed using correlation analysis with the aid of statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 23. Findings from the study show that. Machine learning has significant effect on decision support system on supply chain management of lubricant firms in Anambra state ($T=2.244$, $P=0.006$). Neural networks has significant effect on creative decision skill on supply chain

management of lubricant firms in Anambra state ($T=9.790$, $P=0.009$). The study concludes that AI-powered predictive analytics improved decision-making in supply chain management in lubricant firms in Anambra state, Nigerian. The study recommends that Firms should prioritize data collection, storage, and analysis. Technical expertise is critical for implementing and optimizing neural network algorithms. Firms should consider hiring experts or providing training to existing staff.

METHOD

Research Design

Descriptive research design and causal research design as well as the survey method was used. Descriptive research design will be used to describe some phenomena because it aids a researcher in gathering, summarizing, presenting and interpreting information for the purpose of clarification while the causal research design was used to describe the effect of one variable on another that is establish cause and effect relationship

Sources of Data

Data collection involve gathering of relevant and important data used for conducting a particular research work. It is the basis for acquiring data. Data can be collected in two ways which are; primary data and secondary data. Primary source of data will be used for gathering data in this research work. It is the data collected for the purpose of the research, these are the responses generated or obtained from administered questionnaires (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2003). The questionnaire research instrument will used in this research work to gather information because it helps to access a large number of respondents at a minimal cost. The data collected would be gathered, sorted, and analyzed with the use of Statistical Package for Social Sciences.

Population of the Study

Population is the totality of any group, persons or object which is defined by unique attributes. The population of the study consists of all the staff of Nnamdi Azikwe Nursing library, and medical library, law library and pharmacy library. Therefore the population of interest is twenty (163) staff

Sampling Technique

The stratified random sampling was utilized in this study. This was done by segmenting the workers based on their job status ranging from senior staff, junior staff, contract and casual workers. This technique is appropriate in order to ensure that every element in the sampling frame has an equal opportunity of being selected

Method of Data Collection.

The instrument used for data collection for in this study is the questionnaire, the questionnaire were self-administered. A questionnaire is a structured or semi structured instrument, an array of questions to be answered by persons in order to provide information for a specific purpose. The questionnaire is structured about the research objectives, the research questions and the research hypotheses (Mugenda and Mugenda, 2003). For the purpose of this research, the questionnaire will be based on close-ended questions aimed at generating brief and specific answers from the participants.

Validity Test of Instrument

Validity in research refers to the degree to which a research instrument measures what it intends to measure. The study adopts the content validity test. The research instrument was given to two two lecturers in Public Administration to ensure that the questionnaire was well written and rid of ambiguities after which it was given to the Supervisors for validation so as to ensure that the questionnaire captures the key concepts it is supposed to measure.

Method of Data Analysis.

Statistics such as frequency count and percentages were uses in the analysis of research questions while research hypotheses were tested using correlation analysis and simple regression analysis. The research hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Analysis will be carried out with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

Multiple Regression Analysis

Multiple regression result was employed to test the effect of independent or explanatory variables on the dependent variables. The result of the multiple regression analysis is presented in the tables below.

Table 4.1.1 Summary of the Regression Result

The result of the multiple regressions formulated in chapter three is presented in the tables below.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin - Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.475 ^a	5.226	.5118	.432	.226	30.997	3	153	.000	1.721

a. Predictors: (Constant), FIN, PROM, WRKE

b. Dependent Variable: FMP

Table 3 shows that R² which measures the strength of the effect of independent variable on the dependent variable have the value of 52%. This implies that 21% of the variation in firm performance is explained by variations in financial incentive, promotion and work environment. This was supported by adjusted R² of 51%. In order to check for autocorrelation in the model, Durbin-Watson statistics was employed. Durbin-Watson statistics of 1.721 in table 3 shows that the variables in the model are not auto correlated and that the model is reliable for predications.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	17.346	3	5.782	30.997	.000 ^b
	Residual	59.503	150	.187		
	Total	76.848	153			

a. Dependent Variable: FMP

b. Predictors: (Constant), FIN, PROM, WRKE

The f-statistics value of 30.997 in table 4.5 with f-statistics probability of 0.000 shows that the independent variables has significant effect on dependent variables such as financial incentive, promotion and work environment, can collectively explain the variations in top quality management.

Coefficients of the Model

T-statistics and probability value from the regression result are the effect of individual independent or explanatory variables on the dependent variables. The summary of the result is presented in the table below.

Table 4.2.1 T-Statistics and Probability Value from the Regression Result

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	1.657	.150		11.055	.000	1.362	1.952
	FIN	.145	.020	.363	7.162	.000	.105	.185
	PROMO	.095	.033	.144	2.840	.005	-.161	-.029
	WRKE	.049	.019	.126	2.579	.010	-.087	-.012

a. Dependent Variable: FMP

Table 4.2 shows the coefficient of the individual variables and their probability values. Financial incentive has a regression t-test of 7.162 with a probability value of 0.000 implying that financial incentive variables have a positive and significant effect on firm performance.

On a similar note, promotion variable has a t-test value of 2.840 and a probability value of 0000. This shows that promotion has a positive and significant effect on firm performance. Lastly, work environment has a regression coefficient of 2.579 with a probability value of 0.010. This implies that work environment has a positive and significant effect on organizational performance

Test of Hypotheses

Here, the four hypotheses formulated in chapter one was tested using t-statistics and significance value of the individual variables in the regression result. The essence of this is to ascertain how

significant are the effect of individual independent or explanatory variables on the dependent variables.

Test of Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Financial incentive has no significant effect on organizational productivity of Nnamdi Azikwe University Libraries.

In testing this hypothesis, the t-statistics and probability value in table above is used. Financial incentive variables have a t-statistics of 7.162 and a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that financial incentive has significant effect on organizational productivity of Nnamdi Azikwe University Libraries.

Test of Hypothesis Three

H₀₃: H₀₃: Promotion has no significant effect on organizational productivity of Nnamdi Azikwe University Libraries.

Promotion has a t-statistics of 2.840 and a probability value of 0.001 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that Promotion has significant effect on organizational productivity of Nnamdi Azikwe University Libraries.

Test of Hypothesis Four

H₀₄: Work environment has no significant effect on organizational productivity of Nnamdi Azikwe University Libraries.

Work environment has a t-statistics of 2.579 and a probability value of 0.010 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses and conclude that Work environment has significant effect on organizational productivity of Nnamdi Azikwe University Libraries.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Summary

This chapter contains the summary of major findings, conclusion, recommendations, contribution to knowledge and the suggestions for further research. Thus, the interpretative analysis of the data collected in addition to the test of hypothesis and the discussion of results, resulted in the major findings, which are summarized below:

The following were the major findings of the study:

- Financial incentive has significant effect on organizational productivity of Nnamdi Azikwe University Libraries..
- Promotion has significant effect on organizational productivity of Nnamdi Azikwe University Libraries..
- Work environment has significant effect on organizational productivity of Nnamdi Azikwe University Libraries.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that training, financial incentive, promotion as well as work environment have positive effect on firm performance and such effect is strong and statistically significant. Their coefficients are statistically different from zero at less than 5 percent level of significance. It is obvious to management that training, financial incentive, promotion as well as work environment are sine qua non for stimulating worker's performance in any organization. When promotion are not given, workers tend to express their displeasure through poor performance and non-commitment to their job. It is therefore, important for any organization to consider the needs and feelings of its employees and not just overlook them because "a happy worker they say is a productive worker.' The study concludes that, motivation has significant positive effect on organizational productivity of Nnamdi Azikwe University Libraries.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study.

1. The study also recommends that management should provide effective incentive plan to their employees from time to time to boost their morale for enhanced productivity and performance. The reason is that cash bonuses will encourage them to put more effort in discharging their duties effectively.
2. Management should publicly recognize the efforts of their employees to induce their performance in the work place. Workers promotion and promotion arrears (intrinsic reward) should be implemented as at when due.
3. . Management should provide a conducive environment for actualization of organizational goal, mission and vision

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